

17th ITS European Congress

A Multi-Criteria Methodology for Prioritising Data Quality Tools in ITS

**Rodolfo Da Silva^{1*}, Aristotelis Savva², George Christou³, Nele Dedene⁴, Edwin 't Lam⁵,
Sara F. Guerra De Oliveira⁶, Richard Rek⁷, Christos Laoudias¹, Christos Panayiotou^{1,8}**

1. rgomes01@ucy.ac.cy*, KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence - University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus
2. Public Works Department - Ministry of Transport, Communications and Works, Nicosia, Cyprus
3. ERTICO - ITS Europe, Brussels, Belgium
4. Department Mobility and Public Works, Flemish Government, Brussels, Belgium
5. Transport and Traffic Consultancy, Oulu, Finland
6. Faculty of Civil Engineering, Transportation Engineering and Architecture - University of Maribor, Maribor, Slovenia
7. CEDA Maps a.s., Prague, Czech Republic
8. Department of Electrical and Computer Eng., University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

Abstract

This paper builds on a deliverable produced under the EU project NAPCORE, focused on improving road and traffic data trust, quality, security, sovereignty, and integrity within the TN-ITS framework. While the original work addressed static road data only, here we extend the scope to a cross-domain data quality model and associated assessment method applicable to all transport datasets required by the Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) Directive 2010/40/EU (amended by Directive (EU) 2023/2661) and associated Delegated Regulations.

We propose a set of quality criteria and associated levels that can be measured and compared, providing a common reference for assessing the readiness and interoperability of mobility datasets required under the ITS Directive across Member States. Going beyond the deliverable, we refine this methodology by introducing an AI-specific dimension, recognising that AI-enabled validation and decision-support systems impose additional requirements on data reliability, representativeness, and transparency.

On this basis, the main contribution of the paper is a multi-criteria evaluation methodology that helps road authorities and National Access Point (NAP) operators prioritise which data quality tools to implement first, and determine the quality of the supposed data. The methodology ranks tools according to their expected impact and implementation effort, allowing stakeholders to focus on those tools that most effectively address existing weaknesses and strengthen trust in published datasets. We corrected the original NAPCORE tool ranking algorithm and provided an updated method.

Finally, we discuss how this evaluation methodology translates into minimum recommended quality requirements for AI applications in transport, offering a practical reference for assessing whether transport datasets are sufficiently reliable for AI-based analysis and decision-making (e.g. bias monitoring, provenance, representativeness). Our results show that standardised schemas like mobilityDCAT-AP and feedback loop tools are placed high in the evaluation and are thus recommended for selected users.

Keywords:

Data Quality, Quality Tools, Multi-criteria Evaluation, Artificial Intelligence (AI), National Access Points (NAPs), Road Authorities, NAPCORE, Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS)

Introduction

The ongoing digital shift in the transport sector is changing the way data is collected, managed, and used to support decisions and policy development [1]. As transport systems become more integrated and dependent on data, the quality of that data becomes essential for operational performance and for maintaining trust among users. Within this context, the ITS framework established by Directive 2010/40/EU and amended by Directive (EU) 2023/2661 [2], and its Delegated Regulations provide a structured policy framework that requires Member States to make essential transport datasets available, interoperable, and accessible through NAPs. These datasets, covering static road attributes, dynamic traffic information, and multimodal data, form the foundation for the next generation of intelligent and data-enabled mobility services in Europe.

To facilitate this process, the NAPCORE Project [3] was launched to harmonise and improve the operation and coordination of NAPs across Member States. Among its main outcomes, Deliverable 4.2.7 – *Guide for ensuring the deployment of Trust, Quality, Integrity, Security, and Sovereignty of TN-ITS data: Concepts of data chain evaluation tools* [4] focused on enhancing data aspects within the TN-ITS standard [5], particularly for the exchange of static road data such as speed limits. They are data trust, quality, security, sovereignty, and integrity. Although the deliverable focused on TN-ITS, its approach and conclusions can be applied more broadly to other datasets covered by the ITS Directive. These principles offer a coherent basis for approaching data quality governance across several ITS-related datasets.

In parallel, the wider use of AI in transport management and analytics reinforces the necessity for datasets that are accurate, complete, consistent, and updated. High-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way as to ensure that their operation is sufficiently transparent to enable deployers to interpret a system's output and use it appropriately [6]. The NAPCORE deliverable proposed a structured set of quality criteria and levels, drawing on several European frameworks, to provide a shared language for assessing dataset readiness and guiding improvements. Meeting these minimum quality requirements is essential to limit the risk of bias in AI models and to ensure that AI-based transport services remain reliable, transparent, and fair.

Building on this, the primary objective of this paper is to present a multi-criteria evaluation formula that supports the prioritisation of data quality enhancement tools based on technical impact, organisational feasibility, legal compliance, and business relevance. This methodology proposes a possible roadmap for road authorities and NAP operators to improve dataset governance and transparency.

Finally, improving data quality requires more than technical measures. It also demands changes in organisational routines and governance practices. It is equally important to ensure that high-quality datasets can be discovered by using metadata and interpreted easily, with clear indications of their quality levels and assessment criteria. In this way, we propose concrete next steps as necessary conditions for the transport ecosystem to meet the minimum data-quality standards. This approach is required for reliable and responsible AI applications, while also giving users confidence that their tools are operating on dependable, unbiased data [7].

Objectives

This paper aims to propose a comprehensive methodology for assessing and improving transport data quality within the context of the ITS Directive and its Delegated Regulations, ensuring datasets are AI-ready, interoperable, and trustworthy, by addressing three key objectives:

1. Define a clear set of quality criteria and corresponding levels that can serve as a common reference for evaluating the readiness of ITS Directive datasets across different stakeholders.
2. Develop a multi-criteria evaluation methodology to prioritise data quality enhancement tools, offering a practical roadmap for implementation by road authorities and NAP operators.
3. Present a strong link between data quality and trustworthy AI, showing that robust, explainable, and safe AI-based applications depend on datasets that meet defined minimum quality thresholds.

Background

The ITS Directive and its Delegated Regulations require EU Member States to make key transport datasets available, interoperable, and accessible through National Access Points. While this regulatory framework has significantly increased the volume of data made public across Europe, it has also revealed a persistent challenge: numerous assessments have shown that much of the available data does not meet the minimum quality levels needed for reliable operational use. Variations in data completeness, update frequency, and accuracy remain common, creating uncertainty for organisations that depend on these datasets. These issues are further amplified by the fact that different European frameworks and communities prioritise different quality criteria and, in some cases, apply distinct approaches to the very same criteria and quality levels, as quality can be understood in many ways.

Research and innovation centers which design data-driven and AI-enabled tools for transport applications recognised these limitations very early in their development work. Once AI models started to be incorporated into decision-support systems, traffic analysis, and automation-related functions, it became evident that their performance and reliability were strongly linked to the quality of the data they depend on. Low-quality datasets not only limit analytical value but can also propagate errors through automated workflows, producing biased, misleading, or even unsafe outputs [6, 7].

Methodology

The methodological approach used in this paper builds on the analytical work carried out in NAPCORE Deliverable 4.2.7, expanding it so that it can be applied beyond TN-ITS and across different types of datasets regulated under the ITS Directive. The aim is to combine technical rigour with practical usability for road authorities, NAP operators, and data users. The methodology is organised into three main steps. First, a set of measurable data quality criteria (step 1.1) and associated quality levels (step 1.2) was defined, ensuring consistency with existing European frameworks while making them operational enough to support real-world evaluation. Second, a multi-criteria evaluation methodology (step 2) was developed and applied to identify which tools offer the highest added value for improving data quality. The methodology considers impact, technical complexity, organisational aspects, and business relevance, allowing tools to be prioritised transparently and systematically. Finally, the methodology integrates mechanisms to improve transparency and discoverability using structured metadata (step 3). This ensures that users can easily verify data quality levels and understand how datasets were validated, thereby supporting informed reuse, especially in AI-based applications.

Definition of Data Quality Criteria (Step 1.1)

The first part of the methodology in this paper consisted of validating a set of data quality criteria and quality levels that are both (i) consistent with existing European frameworks and (ii) sufficiently operational to be used for tool prioritisation and, ultimately, for AI-readiness assessment.

The process started with a desk-based analysis of the main European quality frameworks, while deliberately adopting an approach that allows multiple datasets and use cases to be represented either explicitly or through logically generalised constructs. These are already applied in the ITS context, namely the European ITS Platform (EU-EIP) [8] quality framework, the TN-ITS GO [9] quality approach, and the TISA 5-Star Rating [10]. Across these frameworks, the following core criteria were selected for their recurrence in at least two of the referenced European frameworks and retained due to their technical relevance and operational clarity: **Accuracy, Correctness, Timeliness, Latency, Geographic Coverage, and Completeness**. In addition to the European mobility data frameworks analysed, further authoritative standards were considered during the development of this paper, notably ISO 8000-1:2022 (Data Quality) [11] and ISO 19157 (Geographic Information - Data Quality) [12], which provide recognised reference principles for assessing and managing data quality.

These criteria were then harmonised into a single consolidated list that is general enough to apply to other ITS Directive datasets (not only for static speed limits) but still grounded in real operational definitions.

Prioritising these criteria is challenging, as various frameworks interpret and weigh the same dimensions differently. As illustrated in Table 1, frameworks differ not only in the weight assigned to each criterion but also in the way specific criteria are defined and applied.

Table 1 - Comparison of Data Quality Criteria Across Frameworks

Criterion	EU-EIP	TN-ITS GO	TISA
Accuracy	Location accuracy (maximum positional error vs. ground truth)	Positional accuracy of the reference road network	Meter-level accuracy
Correctness	Classification correctness (Road segment)	Classification correctness (Road segment)	Classification correctness (FRC - Functional Road Class)
Timeliness (From – To)	Real-world occurrence → Acceptance at the traffic center	Legal/Physical network change → First publication in the TN-ITS dataset	Real-world change → Event acceptance
Latency (From – To)	Acceptance → Availability (at the Access Point)	Dataset Creation → Availability (by Service Provider)	Periodic data refresh availability (Update cycle)
Coverage	% network covered	% network covered	<i>Coverage is not defined as a standalone criterion</i>
Completeness	% of events correctly detected and published	% of attributes covered	% of road segments (FRC coverage) with a valid attribute

Our review also shows that essential quality criteria, particularly **Consistency** (same road element, attribute or event is represented in a harmonised way across all sources, versions and update cycles) and **Provenance** (ensures traceability of who created or modified the data), are generally not treated as high-priority criteria in existing frameworks. Additionally, emerging **AI-related criteria** such as **Bias monitoring** are often underrepresented [6, 7], despite being critical for trustworthy and safety-relevant AI systems. This highlights the need for a more coherent and comprehensive approach to data quality in mobility-related datasets. However, achieving such harmonisation is not straightforward. Different datasets require different quality criteria metrics depending on their nature, as demonstrated by the work carried out by TISA in its 5-Star Rating, which applies distinct evaluation approaches across various use cases (datasets). However, the quality levels themselves should remain standardised, published, and easily accessible, so that users, particularly in AI contexts, can readily determine whether a dataset is sufficiently

valuable and reliable for their models and tools. Ensuring harmonised quality levels, even when metrics vary by dataset type, is essential for transparency, comparability, and the responsible deployment of AI solutions.

Definition of Quality Levels and Minimum Requirements (Step 1.2)

Concerning quality levels and minimum requirements, the previous European frameworks also reveal a diversity of approaches. For certain datasets, particularly those supported by quantitative metrics or high-granularity attributes, using a larger number of levels may be justified to capture finer distinctions in data quality. However, to support comparability and adoption, we propose a simplified three-level model aligned with EU-EIP and TN-ITS GO conventions. This approach offers a practical balance between analytical detail and usability, with each level corresponding to a typical application context, and expanded to reflect the additional requirements imposed by AI-enabled validation, analysis, and decision-support systems.

- **Low-Quality Level** - Suitable for non-critical, consumer-oriented applications where only basic accuracy, timeliness, and coverage are required. Not recommended for safety-related or AI tasks. Navigation based on Low-Quality Level data is adequate for routine use, though it may lack the precision required in dense or complex environments.
- **Medium-Quality Level** - Ensures a sufficient level for the suggested quality criteria for dependable operational use in mobility systems. This level provides a robust foundation for advanced analytics and supports the reliable deployment of AI-assisted functions, provided that the dataset is regularly updated and validated.
- **High-Quality Level** - Provides the highest degree of the suggested quality criteria. This level is designed for applications that demand exceptional reliability, such as real-time traffic optimisation, high-quality digital twins, and data-driven safety assessments, and incorporates enhanced governance, metadata transparency, and continuous quality monitoring.

In this model, we propose that the Medium-Quality Level serves as the minimum recommended threshold for present AI applications, helping to prevent error propagation and unintended bias. However, as transport datasets increasingly serve as inputs to more advanced AI systems, such as predictive traffic models and automated driving algorithms, the requirements associated with the highest quality level must extend beyond classical dimensions of data quality. Recent studies show that AI models trained on incomplete or unbalanced datasets tend to exhibit biased or unreliable behaviour [13, 14]. Therefore, it is reasonable to expect that within the coming years, the High-Quality Level will become a practical requirement for AI-driven transport applications, supporting long-term trust and adoption.

Multi-Criteria Evaluation Methodology for Prioritising Data Quality Tools (Step 2)

Before introducing this multi-criteria evaluation methodology, it is important to clarify that the assessment of tools is independent of the definition of quality criteria and levels described in the first part (step 1.1, 1.2) of the methodology. The criteria and levels establish what constitutes data quality, while the tool evaluation focuses on how quality can be strengthened in practice. Although separate, both components are connected: the use of certain tools can enable organisations to reach higher quality levels by improving specific quality criteria.

Given this, the latter methodology part introduces a multi-criteria evaluation approach to identify and rank the tools that can most effectively strengthen the data quality of datasets published under the ITS Directive. This methodology, adapted from Deliverable 4.2.7, enables structured comparison of different tools by examining their importance, technical impact, legal feasibility, and business value across the data chain.

The first step involved compiling a comprehensive inventory of tools that support governance functions within the

NAP ecosystem. These tools were grouped into seven operational categories:

- **Semantic validation tools**, including data type checks, enumeration and range checks, and version control mechanisms, are used to ensure that individual data elements and attributes adhere to expected semantic constraints.
- **Syntactic validation tools**, particularly XML (eXtensible Markup Language) validation utilities, which verify compliance with schema structures and technical specifications.
- **Compliance assessment tools**, including self-declaration of Compliance, designed to evaluate adherence to standards, regulations, and implementation guidelines.
- **Security and trust tools**, such as AAA (Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting) services, encryption, provenance tracking, integrity checks, and authentication/authorisation components that safeguard the trust dimension of the dataset.
- **Metadata specification tools**, including the metadata mobilityDCAT-AP [16] schema, which support harmonised dataset documentation and improve discoverability across NAPs.
- **Feedback loop tools**, enabling structured reporting, consultation processes, and user feedback to support continuous quality improvement.
- **Service and assurance tools**, such as SLAs (Service Level Agreements), audits, trust certification schemes, and digital signatures, which ensure transparency, accountability, and reliability in data provision.

A prior analysis of data chain (collection, processing, exchange, integration, and usage) vulnerabilities and their potential countermeasures helped clarify where specific tools can effectively mitigate risks or strengthen trust. Building on this, each tool was mapped to the stakeholders who either operate it or benefit from it across the different stages of the data chain. This mapping provides a clearer understanding of how each tool contributes to improving quality and trust across the end-to-end data ecosystem.

To determine which tools stakeholders should prioritise, a dedicated assessment was carried out using a set of evaluation criteria defined in the deliverable and refined through 20 experts' consultation across 9 Member States. The assessment considered four criteria: (i) the **Level of impact/importance (LI)** on data quality, trust, security, sovereignty and integrity; (ii) the technical **Level of Implementation Complexity (LC)**; (iii) its **Level of Organizational & Legal Complexity (LL)** (all rated 1–9); and (iv) the **Business prospect (BP)**, classified as either immediate (rated 1) or medium-term (rated 0.5) relevance. All tool scoring followed the structured assessment documented in Annex A of Deliverable 4.2.7, ensuring consistency and comparability across all suggested tools.

To produce an overall priority ranking, the methodology applied a weighted average model using the same weighting factors adopted in the deliverable. The Level of Impact (LI) carries a weight of 30%, reflecting its primary importance. Technical Level of Implementation Complexity (LC) contributes 20% but is inverted ($10 - LC$) so that lower-complexity tools score higher. Organisational and Legal Feasibility (LL) accounts for 25%, also inverted ($10 - LL$) to reward tools with fewer institutional barriers. The remaining 25% is assigned to Business Prospect (BP), prioritising tools with immediate practical value.

Refinement of the original approach: During the preparation of this paper, a detailed verification of the original calculation methodology used in NAPCORE Deliverable 4.2.7 revealed numerical inconsistencies. To address this, we provide an updated formula and recalculated results. These corrected values should be considered the authoritative version for subsequent work.

$$\text{Weighted Score (\%)} = \left[0.20 \frac{10 - LC}{10} + 0.30 \frac{LI}{10} + 0.25 \frac{10 - LL}{10} + 0.25 B \right] 100,$$

$$B = \begin{cases} 1 & BP = \text{immediate} \\ 0.5 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Figure 1 - Weighted Score Used to Rank Tools Recommended for Road Authorities

Transparency and Discoverability through Metadata (Step 3)

Ensuring high data quality is only part of the challenge. An equally important requirement is giving users, authorities, service providers, and AI developers the ability to find, interpret, and trust the datasets published on NAPs. This shifts quality assessment from an internal activity carried out by data providers to something visible and meaningful to users, enabling comparability across Member States. In practice, several Member States have already begun adopting visual quality indicators, badges, and simple diagrams within their NAP interfaces, illustrating quality levels or update frequency to make this information more intuitive and accessible to end users.

Even with clear methodologies for assessing data quality and prioritising tools, users still need a straightforward way to verify dataset quality before integrating it into operational systems or AI workflows. Without structured and standardised metadata, high-quality datasets cannot be easily distinguished from weaker ones, which undermines trust, especially where data feeds AI systems that depend heavily on reliability and safety.

Metadata schemas such as mobilityDCAT-AP provide a structured mechanism to address this challenge. They offer harmonised fields through which quality-related attributes can be published, ensuring:

- Discoverability, by making quality metadata searchable and easily retrievable.
- Comparability, by applying common structures across Member States.
- Transparency, by exposing how data is collected, validated, and maintained.
- Traceability, by documenting versions, timestamps, and responsible organisations.

mobilityDCAT-AP is especially valuable due to its Quality Annotation element (data quality vocabulary: *QualityAnnotation*), which allows data providers to document quality criteria, achieved quality levels, assessment methods, timestamps of last validation, and known limitations in a structured and machine-readable form. This helps users, especially AI developers, understand whether a dataset meets the reliability thresholds needed for safe and appropriate use.

Evaluation and Results

The objective of the evaluation was to determine which tools offer the most significant and feasible improvements to data quality within the ITS Directive context. The multi-criteria evaluation was applied to all 30 tools identified in Deliverable 4.2.7 using the weighted model described in Figure 1. Each tool received a priority score reflecting its expected impact on data quality, its technical complexity, organisational and legal feasibility, and business relevance. The scores for each criterion were defined and reviewed by several project partners representing different Member States.

Table 2 presents a sample of data quality tools selected for inclusion in the subsequent evaluation. This sample is illustrative and does not represent the full range of available tools. The full Top 5 ranking for each of the four evaluation criteria, along with the corresponding weighted average percentage scores, is documented in Annex A of Deliverable 4.2.7, where the detailed scoring tables are available for consultation.

Table 2 - Sample of Identified Data Quality Tools Score

Categories	Name of Tool	LC (Complexity)	LI (Importance)	LL (Legal)	BB (Business prospect)	Weighted average of all criteria (%)
Semantic Validation Tools	Data type checks	3	7	3	Immediate	77,50
	Version check	3	7	3	Immediate	77,50
Syntactic Validation Tools	XML Validation Tool	3	7	5	Immediate	72,50
Standardized metadata schema	mobilityDCAT-AP	5	9	5	Immediate	74,50
Feedback Loop	Reporting Tool	5	9	3	Immediate	79,50
	Internal Feedback	5	9	5	Immediate	74,50
Service/Administrative Tools	SLA / Licenses	3	7	5	Immediate	72,50
	Trust Certification	7	9	9	Immediate	60,50

Although **Semantic and Syntactic Validation** tools achieve high weighted average percentage scores, largely due to their relatively low implementation effort and foundational importance, they are considered baseline measures already familiar to many Member States. Beyond these foundational tools, two categories stand out as the highest scoring across Member States.

First, the adoption of **Standardised Metadata Schemas**, particularly mobilityDCAT-AP, appears as one of the most impactful and feasible interventions. This is due to its high importance (LI - score 9) by improving transparency and cross-border comparability without demanding extensive technical resources (LC - score 5). Metadata harmonisation also provides the necessary foundation for machine-readable quality information and seamless discoverability, both of which are essential for AI-ready datasets.

Second, **Feedback-loop** mechanisms score highly because they directly support continuous improvements in data quality. They allow structured feedback, reporting, and verification between data providers and users, helping reduce errors and gradually improve dataset completeness. Their moderate implementation technical effort (LC - score 5) and moderate organisational feasibility (LL - score 3 & 5) make them suitable for short-term adoption. The deliverable also conducted a comprehensive analysis of feedback-loop practices across Member States, revealing diverse approaches shaped by different governance models, maturity levels, and operational constraints.

We also decided to include in this evaluation the **Trust-Certification** tool (from the Service/Administrative tools category) due to its exceptionally high strategic importance (LI – score 9), even though it did not achieve a high weighted average percentage score. This outcome is expected, as its implementation requires significant technical (LC – score 7) and organisational/legal (LL – score 9) effort. Trust-certification tools provide long-term value by strengthening trust, accountability, and regulatory alignment. Despite their demanding implementation requirements, their contribution is substantial: certification offers end users confidence that datasets comply with defined quality thresholds, a requirement that is becoming increasingly critical for downstream AI applications.

Next Steps

Building on these results, several next steps can help further mature and operationalise the proposed methodology. A key priority is to **define quantitative metrics for each quality level**, enabling a shift from qualitative descriptions to measurable thresholds. Drawing on the TISA 5-Star approach, these metrics would allow reproducible assessment of the suggested quality criteria, supporting automated checks and cross-country comparison.

In parallel, future work should also reconsider and refine **AI-related criteria** such as **Bias monitoring**: (i) Representativeness of the dataset (across geographic, socio-economic, and operational contexts), (ii) data Provenance and Traceability, (iii) presence of Historical Bias in the source data, (iv) Bias Discrimination, (v) Semantic Consistency across datasets, and (vi) explicit Documentation of Assumptions and Limitations, in line with emerging

governance frameworks such as the AI Act and guidance from the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights [6, 15]. Based on empirical observations and internal analyses, we have identified several needs linked to these Bias monitoring criteria, such as improving coverage in rural and peri-urban regions, addressing biases caused by data collected mainly in high-traffic areas, and mitigating demographic distortions present in crowdsourced datasets. Likewise, floating-car and connected-vehicle datasets tend to over-represent newer and more expensive vehicles, limiting the representativeness of traffic insights in areas with older fleets. A more detailed definition of geographic coverage and completeness would also help reduce these asymmetries and lower the risk of biased AI outputs.

Another direction for future work is to **test and validate the criteria and tools** through cross-border or multi-city pilots, ensuring that the methodology works consistently across different governance models and operational settings. Such pilots would allow refinement of the criteria and reveal practical implementation issues not visible in desk-based analysis and could be integrated into ongoing initiatives such as the TISGRADE project [17].

Finally, future work should consider embedding the quality methodology into **continuous monitoring environments**, enabling automated checks, alerts, and periodic reassessment of datasets over time. Integrating quality monitoring directly into NAPs, road authority workflows, or AI development pipelines would support ongoing quality assurance and sustained alignment with regulatory and operational needs.

Together, these next steps would significantly contribute to a harmonised, measurable, and AI-ready data quality ecosystem for the European transport domain.

Conclusions

This study shows that strengthening the quality, reliability, and interoperability of transport datasets requires a structured and tool-supported approach. Using a multi-criteria evaluation across different tools, the study identified clear prioritisation patterns shared by several Member States and can be used to identify priority measures that represent the most effective way to improve the quality and eligibility of data sets published under the ITS Directive for the use of artificial intelligence. Although semantic and syntactic validation tools are essential baseline elements, the greatest strategic benefit comes from measures that enhance transparency, support continuous improvement, and provide formal assurance.

Standardised metadata schemas, especially mobilityDCAT-AP, were identified as the most impactful and feasible measures. Their adoption allows quality information to become visible, machine-readable, and comparable across Member States, forming the foundation for AI-ready datasets. Feedback-loop mechanisms also play an essential role by supporting structured interaction between providers and users and helping reduce persistent data issues. Trust-certification tools offer long-term benefits by reinforcing accountability and user confidence, particularly for safety-critical or AI-driven applications.

Together, these categories form a coherent roadmap for strengthening data-quality governance under the ITS Directive. Their combined adoption can transform data quality from a compliance requirement into an active, measurable, and trustworthy aspect of European mobility datasets. As transport systems increasingly rely on data-driven and AI-based processes, these tools will likely be essential for maintaining datasets that are accurate, consistent, transparent, and suitable for use.

References

1. European Commission, Joint Research Centre. (2024). *EU Transport Research & Innovation Status Assessment Report 2024*. Retrieved from <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

2. Directive (EU) 2023/2661 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 November 2023, amending Directive 2010/40/EU regarding the framework for the deployment of Intelligent Transport Systems. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/2661>
3. NAPCORE. (2021–2024). *National Access Point Coordination Organisation for Europe (NAPCORE)*. Funded by the European Union under the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF). <https://www.napcore.eu>
4. NAPCORE. (2024). Deliverable 4.2.7 – *Guide for ensuring the deployment of Trust, Quality, Integrity, Security, and Sovereignty of TN-ITS data: Concepts of data chain evaluation tools*. Retrieved from https://www.napcore.eu/documents/M4.2.7_Final_version.pdf
5. CEN/TS 17268:2021. *Technical Specification for TN-ITS data exchange formats*. European Committee for Standardisation.
6. Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (Artificial Intelligence Act), OJ L 234, 12.7.2024
7. International Transport Forum (2025), *AI for Transport Authorities: Principles and Practical Guidance*, OECD Publishing, Paris. Retrieved from <https://www.itf-oecd.org/>
8. European ITS Platform – EU-EIP. (2016 – 2021). Retrieved from <https://www.its-platform.eu>
9. Transport Network – Intelligent Transport Systems Go - TN-ITS GO. (2018 - 2021). Retrieved from <https://tn-its.eu/>
10. Traveller Information Services Association. (2025, October 21). *RTTI 5-Star Rating Specification for Real-Time Traffic Information*. Retrieved from <https://tisa.org/publication-of-5-star-rating-specification-for-real-time-traffic-information/>
11. ISO, “ISO 8000-1:2022 – Data quality — Part 1: Overview,” International Organisation for Standardisation, Geneva, Switzerland, 2022.
12. ISO, “ISO 19157:2013 – Geographic information — Data quality,” International Organisation for Standardisation, Geneva, Switzerland, 2013.
13. Ferrara, E. (2024). *Fairness and bias in artificial intelligence: A brief survey of sources, impacts, and mitigation strategies*. AI, 4(1), 8–28. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ai4010002>
14. Fernández-Llorca, D., García-Garrido, M. A., Parra-Alonso, I., et al. (2024). *Attribute annotation and bias evaluation in visual datasets for autonomous driving systems*. Journal of Big Data, 11, Article 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-024-00976-9>
15. EU Agency for Fundamental Rights, *Data Quality and Artificial Intelligence: Mitigating Bias and Error to Protect Fundamental Rights*, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2019.
16. MobilityDCAT-AP. Metadata schema for mobility data exchange. Retrieved December 8, 2024, from <https://mobilitydcat-ap.github.io/mobilityDCAT-AP/releases/index.html>
17. TISGRADE. (2025–2028). Traffic management Information Services upGRADE Europe (TISGRADE). Funded by the European Union under the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF).